

"KNOWLEDGE, PERCEPTIONS, AND ATTITUDES OF TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS AT LAKKA GOVERNMENT HOSPITAL REGARDING RECURRENT TB DISEASE"

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in Sierra Leone. Recurrent TB (either relapse or reinfection) is a major challenge for treatment success and control programs. Being aware of patients' knowledge, attitudes and perceptions is critical to developing effective interventions. **Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 150 TB patients (in-patients and out-patients) at Lakka Government Hospital, Sierra Leone, between April and September 2022. A structured questionnaire was used to measure socio-demographics, knowledge (10 items), attitudes (3 items) and perceptions (4 items) of recurrent TB. Data were analyzed by using SPSS version 21 and presented in frequencies and percentages. **Results:** Of the 150 patients surveyed, 29.3% were suffering from recurrent TB. Knowledge on recurrent TB was poor: good knowledge was found in 26.7% of participants, average knowledge in 39.3% and poor knowledge in 34%. Of the 77.7% who responded to the

question, 54% had a good attitude towards TB prevention and treatment and 30.7% had poor attitudes. Perceptions were poor with only 66.7% being classified as poor and 33.3% as good. There were widespread misunderstandings concerning the causes and transmission of TB such as TB being caused by sexual intercourse or witchcraft. **Conclusion:** The majority of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital had poor knowledge and negative perceptions about recurrent TB although good attitudes towards treatment were present. Efforts at health

education and counseling are urgently needed to clear misconceptions, increase awareness, and improve patient participation in TB control.

KEYWORDS: Recurrent Tuberculosis, Patient Knowledge, Attitudes and Perceptions.

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to assess the knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital about recurrent TB disease and the risk factors associated with it. Tuberculosis (TB) is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, mainly infecting the lungs, digestive organs, lymph, and bones.^[1] It is a transmissible disease that causes mortality by only one organism and is a curable disease.^[2] Primary TB occurs in patients who have never been treated for TB or who have received less than 1 month of anti-TB treatment.

TB is the highest infectious disease that cause mortality in the world, compared to malaria and HIV/AIDS.^[3] It affects 10 million people worldwide, resulting in approximately 1.2 million mortalities in HIV-negative patients and 251,000 deaths in HIV-affected patients in 2018. The disease's impact is not only focused on health but also leads to severe financial crises in underdeveloped countries.^[4]

TB is derived from bacteria of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) and poses a serious threat to public health worldwide.^[5] Approximately 10 million people still infected with the disease each year.^[6] In Africa, such as rural Malawi, Kenya, Uganda, and South Africa, TB is believed to be sexually transmitted, caused by smoking, alcohol, hard work, exposure to the cold, hereditary factors, and coming in contact with other TB patients.

The WHO states that one of the reasons for delay detection of TB disease among the community is absence of knowledge in the signs and symptoms of TB, and stigma is also one of the factors leading to late diagnosing of TB disease.^[7]

In 2017, TB caused about 1.6 million deaths globally, and in 2019, there were an estimated 10 million new TB cases worldwide.^[8] Africa is the second highest TB endemic continent in the world.^[9]

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Patients, who usually complete their treatment for Tuberculosis, and declared cure are under high risk of developing recurrent TB disease, as a result of relapse or reinfection.

The risk factors which result in increased recurrent Tuberculosis are drug-resistance, smoking, HIV infection with low CD4 lymphocyte counts, substance use, chronic lung disease, sputum smear-positive disease, and cavity pulmonary disease.^[10]

Also, because recurrent TB disease is another way of transferring TB, in the general population, and patients who have completed their treatment and declared cure, but later develop TB disease again, and this contribute to the increase in TB cases.

Therefore clear, correct knowledge, perception and attitude in TB patients is important to reduce the number of TB cases and this is little known in developing countries, especially Sierra Leone.

JUSTIFICATION

TB control programs in endemic places hardly monitor patients after treatment completion and. Recurrent TB disease contribute to the increased mortality and risk of transmission of the Tuberculosis,^[11] and there is little knowledge about recurrent TB disease and their risk factors associated with them, in developing countries especially sierra Leone.

Therefore, this study was done to create understanding, change the misperceptions and wrong knowledge and attitudes among TB Patients about recurrence TB disease and the risk factors associated with it, although similar studies has been done in certain part of Africa such as Malawi, but this has not been done or published in Sierra Leone.

AIM AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

AIM

The Aim of this study is to assess knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes of TB patients at Lakka government Hospital about the recurrence TB disease and risks factors associated with the recurrence TB disease.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- 1) To assess the knowledge of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital about recurrence TB disease.

- 2) To assess the Attitude of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital about recurrent TB disease.
- 3) To assess the perceptions of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital about recurrent TB disease

Recurrent TB is a repeat occurrence of TB disease in patients, occurring after the first TB disease has been declared as clinically cured according to WHO guidelines.^[12]

Recurrent TB patients are those who have initially been treated for TB, were confirmed cured or finished their treatment, and are recently again diagnosed with a recurrent episode of TB (Gadoev et al. 2017)^[13] Between 1994 and 2006, there were 5,723 tuberculosis notifications, 3,731 of which were culture-positive. Fifteen (0.4%) patients had recurrent TB disease over a mean 5.7 years of follow-up. Recurrent TB was attributable to re-activation (indistinguishable strains) in 11 (73%) cases and to re-infection (different strains) in four (27%).^[14]

Among 118 successfully treated TB patients, 36% were diagnosed again with active TB within the next 22 months, from the number re-diagnosed, with 52% of these re-diagnoses being sputum smear-positive for Acid Fast Bacilli (AFB). Patients who are categorized to complete their treatment usually have higher smear-positive recurrence when compared to those classified as cured.^[13]

The recurrence rates can be used to determine the effectiveness of TB control programs.^[15] Recurrent TB occurs due to relapse of frequent infection regardless of symptomatic and microbiological "cure" or as a result of re-infection. Estimation of the reoccurrence are not consistent and occur in different ways among populations due to variation in treatment regimens and infection risks.^[16]

There are generally two types of recurrent TB: endogenous reactivation and exogenous reinfection. Successfully treated TB patients experience a three times higher death rate than the general population. The contribution of reactivation and reinfection to the burden of TB recurrence remains unclear and may have a negative impact on public health.^[17]

Relapse disease is a subsequent episode of tuberculosis (TB) caused by the reactivation/reemergence of the original infecting strain of *M. tuberculosis* (MTB).^[18] Endogenous reactivation refers to incident cases of TB that occur as a result of re-

activation/reemergence of the initial infection contained by the host immune response, in the case of individuals with latent TB infection or the application of chemotherapy in patients with active TB disease.^[12] Reactivation is defined as re-inflammation with the same *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strain as diagnosed in the initial episode of the disease.^[19]

Recurrent TB disease constitutes 5-30% of the TB burden, with higher proportions found in high-prevalence settings. Recurrence may be due to endogenous relapse or exogenous reinfection.^[20] Re-infection is the infection with a different *M. tuberculosis* strain than isolated in the previous episode(s) of the disease.^[19] In TB endemic places, reinfection is the main cause for increase in recurrence rates.^[5]

Differentiating between relapse and reinfection is crucial for monitoring the successful outcome of control programs and creating clear knowledge on the immune responses to TB. By distinguishing between the two mechanisms of the types of recurrent TB, such as relapse and reinfection, more effective TB control patterns could be adopted to attain better TB control.^[5]

Either endogenous reactivation or exogenous infection could result in a new episode of TB even after a complete anti-TB treatment.^[21] Comparing the isolates from the first and second episodes of TB could distinguish between these two different causes. High rates of relapse may indicate unsuccessful treatment, while a high rate of recurrence due to reinfection suggests a failure to develop protective immunity after the first episode and is associated with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection.

Distinguishing between relapse and reinfection requires molecular marker analysis of cultures from both episodes. Genotyping methods for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) allow researchers to discriminate relapse and re-infection. These "mixed-strain" or "heterogeneous" infections arise either through sporadic mutation (clonal heterogeneity) or host acquisition of more than one strain of *M. tuberculosis* (polyclonal heterogeneity), either at the time of infection or through serial reinfection.^[22]

Recurrent TB disease is associated with various risk factors, including drug-resistance, smoking, HIV infection, substance use, chronic lung disease, sputum smear-positive disease, and cavity pulmonary disease. These factors can increase the risk of recurrence TB due to their suitability for small numbers of mycobacteria to continue after treatment or due to

immune incompetence. Poor medication adherence to anti-tuberculosis drugs and a patient's immune status can also result in recurrence TB disease.^[10]

To achieve meaningful reductions in TB incidence and mortality, it is crucial to understand the risk factors associated with recurrent TB and their interaction. Factors such as duration of treatment, bactericidal/bacteriostatic activity of medications, mode of administration, irregular drug intake, initial drug resistance, smoking, and alcoholism have been identified as risk factors.^[13]

Recurrent TB contributes significantly to the significant disease burden in settings where TB is endemic.^[23] It poses a major threat to TB control programs, especially given the persistent vulnerability of HIV-infected patients to tuberculosis and the higher propensity of recurrent disease being due to resistant MTB strains.^[18]

Prevention and treatment of recurrent TB include the standard six-month TB treatment regimen for all new and retreatment drug-susceptible TB cases, rapid molecular-based drug susceptibility testing (DST),^[18] and secondary preventative therapy (sPT). To prevent relapse, TB treatment guidelines should be recommended, extended treatment for TB cases with cavities on chest radiographs, and delayed bacterial clearance from sputum.^[24]

Misconceptions also exist. Misconceptions about transmission of disease lead to discrimination like separate utensils for food or drink.^[25]

METHODS

This study aimed to investigate the knowledge, attitude, and perception of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital about recurrent TB disease and associated risk factors. The research was conducted between February and September 2022, using a cross-sectional quantitative study design. The study was conducted at the Lakka Government Hospital Freetown Western area urban, which is made up of two departments: outpatients and inpatients. The inpatients department is divided into female and male wards, with the female final stage being commonly called white house, while the male final stage is commonly called.

The study targeted both outpatient and inpatient TB patients, incorporating both females and males diagnosed with active TB disease for their first, second, and many times. Participants were eligible for this study if they were within the age range of 18 years old and above and if

they were diagnosed with active and recurrent TB disease. Participants were excluded from this study if they were below the age of 18 years and also if they were not diagnosed with active TB disease, such as those who just reported during data collection period or those whose results were in the laboratory and were not confirmed to be TB positive.

The sample size for this study was 150, with a total of 85 outpatient and 104 inpatient patients. The distribution of questionnaires per department was determined using a proportional formula of $[Q = (m/N) \times n]$. The study was approved by the Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences Research Committee COMAHS, and ethical consent was taken from participants. Participants were allowed to leave the studies as they wish, but additional questionnaires were provided to address this issue.

A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data. These Self-administered questionnaires were developed, and adopted from a questionnaire of a survey done in West Africa toward COVID -19 for public health intervention, and then it was modified to meet my study objectives at Lakka Government Hospital.

Data was imported into an excel sheet and electronically transferred to an SPSS software version 21 for presentations and analysis. The knowledge section of the questionnaire, had sixteen questions, of which ten (10) questions, were scored. The responder was awarded a plus one for correct answers and a zero for incorrect responses, and the total was calculated and classified as good knowledge for ($\geq 8/80\%$ correct answers), average knowledge (between 5 to 7/50-70% correct answers), and poor knowledge ($\leq 4/40\%$ correct answers).

In the attitude area of the questionnaire, four questions were asked, of which three (3) of them were scored. Participant was awarded plus one for correct attitude and zero for wrong attitude. Participants were classified to have positive attitude, when their total correct answers were between two to three and classified as to have negative attitude when their total correct answers are one and below.

In the perception section, five questions were asked, of which four (4) of were scored, with the correct answer earning a plus one and the incorrect response receiving a zero. The respondent was graded as good for (three to four correct answers) and categorized to have poor perception for (two correct answers and below).

The data was summarized in a tabular form as frequencies and percentage.

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3.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

- 1) The study was approved by the department of pharmaceutical sciences research committee COMAHS
- 2) Ethical consent was taken from participants
- 3) Participants were allowed to leave the studies as they wish
- 4) This was addressed by given additional questionnaires

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results

DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL BACKGROUND ANALYSIS

The sample size for this study was 150, and questionnaires were distributed proportional to the calculated sample size, from the distributed questionnaires,

Table 1: Shows socio-demographic characteristics of TB patients.

Socio-Demographic	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Age of patient		
18-33	99	66.0
34-49	43	28.7
>50	8	5.3
Gender of patient		
Female	74	49.3
Male	76	50.7
Number of dependent		
zero	32	21.3
one	41	27.3
two	23	15.3
three	12	8.0
four	4	2.7
>five	38	25.3
Marital status of patient		
Single	90	60.0
Married	49	32.7
Divorced	9	6.0
Widow	2	1.3
religion of patient		
Christian	64	42.7
Muslim	84	56.0
Atheist	2	1.3
African traditional Religion	0	0.0
others	0	0.0
resident of patient		

City/town(urban)	76	50.7
Town(suburban)	27	18.0
Village(rural)	47	31.3
Educational level of patient	40	26.7
Primary school	48	32.0
Junior secondary	46	30.7
Senior secondary/high school	2	1.3
Postgraduate	14	9.3
Vocational		
Number of years of education	43	28.7
0-6years	46	30.7
>6-10years	61	40.7
>10years		
occupation of patient	7	4.7
Academic/researcher	11	7.3
Entrepreneur	3	2.0
Private servant	47	31.3
Student	82	54.7
Unemployed		
Number of times admitted	106	70.7
First time	41	27.3
Second time	3	2.0
Many times		

ANALYSIS OF KNOWLEDGE LEVEL OF TB PATIENTS

The scores of patients in table 5, revealed, that only 40(26.7%) of the patients have good knowledge, while 59(39.3%) have average knowledge, and 51(34.0%) has poor knowledge. Table 2 shows the questions that were used to assess the knowledge of TB Patients about Recurrent TB disease. Majority 116(77.3%) of the TB patients have knowledge about recurrent TB disease, majority 63(42.0%) of the patients get and obtained their information from family and friends.

Majority 80(53.3%) of the participants believed that recurrent TB occur through transmission, majority 131(87.3%) of the TB patients believed that recurrent TB is another way of increasing TB cases, while huge portion of the participants, stated that recurrent is not another way of transferring TB disease, huge number 107(71.3%) were worried that they or close person may develop recurrent TB after recovery, and majority 81(54.0%) of the respondents know of people who have developed recurrent TB disease. The majority 77(51.3%) of TB Patients understood that, recurrent TB can be transfer, through respiratory droplets when an infected person cough, sneeze or speak, most 131(87.3%) of participants agreed that recurrent TB is another way of increasing TB cases, 133(88.7%) of the patients knew that, the main clinical symptoms of recurrent TB are chest pain, fever, muscles pain,

dry cough, and shortness of breath, while most 123(82%) of the patients knew that, stuff nose, running nose, and sneezing are less common in person who developed recurrent TB.

Majority 72(48.0%) of the participants understood that, there is current vaccine that can protect them from developing recurrent TB, most 83(55.3%) of the respondents knew that, there is no effective cure for recurrent TB disease, but only early symptomatic and supportive treatment can help most patients recover from the infection, 97(64.7%) of the patients knew that, not all patients with tuberculosis will develop recurrent TB disease after recovery, majority 75(50.0%) of the participants agreed that, isolation and treatment of people who developed recurrent TB disease are effective way to reduce the spread of TB, majority knew that recurrent TB can be diagnosed by isolating the bacteria from sputum, most 87(58.0%) of patients understood that, patients with HIV infection and who abuse substances are at higher risk of developing recurrent TB disease. From our findings, we noticed that, people with drugs resistance, who smoke and drink alcohol, those with HIV infection, those who abuse substance use, people with chronic lungs disease, sputum-smear positive disease, cavity pulmonary disease, those with compromised immune system, are at higher risk of developing recurrent TB disease after recovery

ANALYSIS OF ATTITUDE LEVEL OF TB PATIENTS

The attitude portion of table 5 show that, 104(69.3%) of the TB patients have good attitude, while 46(30.7%) of the respondents have poor attitude. Most 83(55.3%) of patients decided to go to government hospital if they are diagnosed with recurrent TB disease, majority 85(56.7%) of the participants decided to do regular medical check up to detect recurrent TB at early stage, most 128 (85.3%) of TB Patients are ready to follow any procedure, that can help prevent recurrent TB disease, 139(92.7%) decided to stay away from relatives and friends to prevent transmission.

ANALYSIS OF PERCEPTIONS LEVEL OF PATIENTS

In Table 5, Majority 100(66.7%) of the patients have poor perceptions, while 50(33.4%) have good perceptions. Most 95(63.3%) of the respondents decided to go to government hospital, if they suspect they have developed recurrent TB disease, majority 82(54.7%) of the TB patients knew that, they are under risk of developing recurrent TB disease after recovery, most 74(49.3%) of the patients have the thought that prompt measures are always taken to prevent recurrent TB disease.

According to our study, majority 81(54.0%) do think that anyone who lives and works in high risk setting such as health care workers, prisoners and other close setting should be tested for recurrent TB disease, majority 132(88.0%) of the patients think that they will be allowed for regular check after recovery from Tuberculosis.

SCORES SHOWING THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PERCEPTIONS LEVEL OF PATIENTS ABOUT RECURRENT TB DISEASE

Table 5: Shows scores of TB patients on their knowledge, attitude and perceptions.

No	Variable	Categories	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
1	Knowledge level	Good knowledge	40	26.7
		average knowledge	59	39.3
		Poor knowledge	51	34.0
		Total	150	100
2	Attitude level	Positive attitude	104	69.3
		Negative attitude	46	30.7
		Total	150	100
3	Perception level	Good perception	50	33.3
		Poor perception	100	66.7
		Total	150	100

DISCUSSION

This study examined the knowledge, attitudes and perceptions of TB patients at Lakka Government Hospital concerning recurrent TB. Nearly one-third of the respondents (29.3%) were suffering from recurrent TB disease, which highlights the importance of relapse and reinfection as obstacles to TB control in Sierra Leone. Recurrent tuberculosis (TB) is also correlated with delayed diagnosis, treatment failure, drug resistance, and poor therapeutic compliance.^[1,2]

Knowledge of recurrent TB

Overall, the knowledge of participants about recurrent TB was generally very low, with only 26.7% showing good knowledge and more than one-third (34%) scoring poorly on the knowledge component. There were myths, such as the idea that the recurrence of TB is due to sexual activity or witchcraft. Similar false beliefs have been reported in studies from South Africa and Ethiopia, where cultural beliefs play an important role in patient perception of TB transmission.^[3,4] The findings are consistent with evidence that limited patient education contributes to poor understanding of the pathophysiology of TB and increases vulnerability to relapse.^[5]

beliefs about TB prevention and treatment

More than half of participants (54%) showed positive attitudes toward treatment and prevention, indicating a potential willingness to adhere to treatment and prevention recommendations. This is similar to evidence from Uganda where patients revealed good treatment attitudes despite knowledge deficits.^[6] However, about one-third of our respondents had low attitudes, representing an ongoing burden of stigma, treatment fatigue, and mistrust towards health services. A previous study in Sierra Leone reported that stigma and misconceptions are still major barriers to treatment completion,^[7] which may partly account for the ongoing TB burden seen.

Perceptions of recurrent TB

Perceptions was the lowest domain: two-thirds (66.7%) of patients' perceptions of recurrent TB were poor. There was a failure to distinguish relapse from reinfection and a poor awareness of the significance of completing therapy. Equally negative perceptions have been described in Nigeria and India where the majority of patients considered recurrent TB to be independent of treatment compliance.^[8, 9] In contrast, data from China and Brazil have shown more positive patient perceptions that may reflect strong public health communication and patient education strategies.^[10,11]

Implications for Sierra Leone TB control

The results indicate that lack of knowledge, negative perceptions and continued misconceptions may compromise TB control activities in Sierra Leone. Recurrent TB not only adds to morbidity of the patient, but also due to persistence, it threatens the general community due to continued transmission and drug resistance for TB.^[12] Patient education and counseling in health facilities, culturally appropriate communication, and participation of cured TB patients as peer educators are some possible strategies for countering misconceptions and enhancing adherence to treatment.^[13,14] In line with the WHO End TB strategy, health systems should ensure that education, stigma reduction, and psychosocial support are incorporated into TB services to reduce relapse and improve outcomes of care.^[15]

CONCLUSION

This study shows that although TB patients attending Lakka Government Hospital display some positive attitudes towards treatment, their knowledge and perception of recurrent TB still needs to be improved. There are significant misconceptions regarding cause,

transmission and prevention and almost one third of patients already experience recurrent disease. Targeted and culturally sensitive health education, sustained patient counselling, and increased engagement in the community are required to address these gaps. Such interventions are critical for decreasing recurrence, enhancing treatment outcomes and furthering national TB control agendas in Sierra Leone.

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